

Angelo Leogrande^{1*°}

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

°LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

Net outflows of foreign direct investment as a percentage of GDP

Decreased by 12.97% between 2013 and 2020

Foreign direct investment refers to direct investment equity flows in an economy. It is the sum of equity capital, reinvestment of earnings, and other capital. Direct investment is a category of cross-border investment associated with a resident in one economy having control or a significant degree of influence on the management of an enterprise that is resident in another economy. Ownership of 10 percent or more of the ordinary shares of voting stock is the criterion for determining the existence of a direct investment relationship. This series shows net outflows of investment from the reporting economy to the rest of the world and is divided by GDP.

Net outflows of foreign direct investment as a percentage in 2020. In 2020, data on "Net outflows of foreign direct investment as a percentage of GDP" show a varied landscape among different countries, highlighting significant differences in global economic dynamics. At the top of the ranking are Cyprus, Hong Kong SAR, China, and Ireland, each with a score of 100%. This result indicates a high intensity of net foreign direct investment relative to GDP, suggesting that these countries are strong exporters of capital, likely due to favorable economic policies, an attractive business environment, and efficient management of financial resources. Following closely are Singapore with 75.2% and Luxembourg with 73.8%, both maintaining a dominant position, demonstrating significant foreign investment activity. Switzerland, with 72.6%, and the Netherlands, with 64.3%, follow in the list, consolidating their reputations as global financial hubs with open and competitive economies. Outside this leading group, countries like Azerbaijan (56.2%) and Myanmar (55.6%), despite being relatively high, reflect a mix of factors such as natural resources and economic policies that incentivize foreign investments. Ethiopia and Uruguay, both with 53.5%, represent interesting cases of emerging economies with a strong outward orientation. Similarly, Finland (53.2%) and Kuwait (53.1%) show high levels of net outflows of foreign direct investment, suggesting solid integration into global markets. Canada, with 51.7%, and Thailand, with 50.7%, exhibit a strong presence of outgoing capital, indicating an economic strategy focused on significant foreign investments. Germany and Japan, with scores of 50.2% and 49.6%, respectively, despite being advanced economies, show a balance between incoming and outgoing capital, with a slight prevalence of the latter. Similarly, Sweden with 49.6% and Spain with 48.9% maintain a good level of net foreign investments, followed by France with 48.8%, reflecting a significant commitment to global economic integration. Countries like Mauritius (48.3%), Denmark (47.7%), and the United Kingdom (47.6%) confirm their position as attractive investment destinations, while Qatar (47.2%) and the United Arab Emirates (47.1%) continue to benefit from liberal economic policies and rich natural resources. Likewise, Israel with

¹Assistant Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrande.culture@lum.it, Strada Statale 100 km 18, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia.

47.1% and the Czech Republic with 46.9% show high economic competitiveness, supported by strong foreign investments. In the range between 40% and 47%, we find a group of countries including Slovakia, the Republic of Korea, Malaysia, and Lebanon, all with percentages around 45%, suggesting significant economic activity but not at the level of market leaders. Russia with 45.1%, Zimbabwe with 44.9%, and Georgia with 44.8% demonstrate economies in transition or emerging with a strong outflow of capital. Countries such as Saudi Arabia (44.5%), Tanzania (44.5%), and Chile (44.4%) reflect diversified economies with a significant focus on foreign investments. Further down, Oman and South Africa, both with 44%, and Lithuania with 43.7%, represent robust economies with good integration into global markets. Colombia (43.4%), Ivory Coast (43.1%), and Poland (43.1%) continue to strengthen their positions through foreign investments, while countries like Bulgaria and China, both with 42.9%, show strong economic strategies but with room for growth. The United States, with 42.4%, and Italy, with 42.3%, reflect advanced economies with significant foreign investment activity, followed by countries like Estonia and Slovenia with 42.2%. Honduras (42.1%), the Philippines (42.1%), and North Macedonia (42%) complete this group with relevant international economic activity.

Net outflows of foreign direct investment as a percentage between 2013 and 2020. Among the countries with the most notable increases, Ireland stands out with an increase in net outflows of foreign direct investment, rising from 45.4% of GDP in 2013 to 100% in 2020, recording an absolute change of 54.6 percentage points, equivalent to a relative increase of 120.26%. This significant increase can be attributed to Ireland's ability to attract foreign investments thanks to a favorable tax environment and an economic policy oriented towards international openness. Cyprus also showed a considerable increase, rising from 53.5% to 100%, with an absolute change of 46.5 percentage points and a relative increase of 86.92%. This reflects the economic stabilization and improvement of the country's financial conditions during the period considered, despite the previous financial crisis turmoil. Hong Kong SAR, China, although with a less marked increase compared to the previous cases, still saw a significant rise of 44.93%, with net outflows of foreign direct investment rising from 69% to 100%. Hong Kong's position as a global financial center has certainly played a crucial role in this context. On the contrary, many countries have recorded a decrease in net outflows of foreign direct investment as a percentage of GDP. The most striking case is Belgium, which saw a decrease from 62.6% to 35.3%, with an absolute change of -27.3 percentage points, equivalent to a relative decrease of 43.61%. This decline could be linked to various factors, including changes in economic policies, political or economic instability, or reduced attractiveness of the country for foreign investors. Hungary also experienced a drastic decrease, from 62.5% to 37.5%, with an absolute change of -25 percentage points and a relative decline of 40%. Similarly, Austria saw a reduction of 35.65%, dropping from 56.1% to 36.1%. These decreases may indicate a change in economic conditions and investors' risk perception. Other countries that have registered significant decreases include Mauritius, with a reduction of 45.73% (from 89% to 48.3%), and Luxembourg, with a decrease of 26.2% (from 100% to 73.8%). These declines may reflect a series of factors, including increasing international competition for attracting investments, internal regulatory changes, and global economic dynamics negatively affecting investor confidence. Countries like Japan, Germany, and Canada have seen only slight decreases in their net outflows of foreign direct investment as a percentage of GDP, with variations of -4.06%, -1.57%, and -2.08%, respectively. These relatively moderate reductions may indicate economic stability that has allowed these countries to maintain a certain level of attractiveness for foreign investments despite global economic challenges. It is interesting to note that some emerging and developing countries, such as Brazil, Argentina, and India,

have recorded significant decreases in their net outflows of foreign direct investment. For example, Brazil saw a reduction of 15.81%, dropping from 48.7% to 41%, while Argentina had a decrease of 19.07%, from 49.3% to 39.9%. These declines can be attributed to a combination of political instability, internal economic problems, and changes in global investment conditions. Countries like China and Russia, despite being large economies with a significant global presence, recorded decreases of 14.03% and 16.01%, respectively. These declines likely reflect internal challenges and geopolitical tensions affecting investors' risk perception. In summary, the analysis of net outflows of foreign direct investment as a percentage of GDP between 2013 and 2020 reveals a complex and varied picture. On one hand, countries like Ireland and Cyprus have shown a remarkable ability to attract foreign investments, while on the other, many countries, including many in Europe and developing countries, have experienced significant reductions. These variations indicate changing global economic dynamics, internal economic policies, and local conditions influencing investors' decisions. Analyzing this data helps to better understand the factors contributing to a country's economic competitiveness and attractiveness in the global foreign direct investment landscape.

Conclusions. Between 2013 and 2020, the value of net outflows of foreign direct investment as a percentage of GDP globally decreased by 12.97%, dropping from 51.6 units to 44.90%, corresponding to a variation of -6.69 units. However, some countries saw significant growth in net outflows of foreign direct investment as a percentage of GDP, including Ireland with +120.26%, Cyprus with +86.92%, Hong Kong with +44.93%, Switzerland with +28.72%, and Singapore with +28.33%. Conversely, some countries experienced much lower trends in net outflows of foreign direct investment as a percentage of GDP compared to the period average, including Zambia with -30.00%, Austria with -35.65%, Hungary with -40.00%, Belgium with -43.61%, and Mauritius with -45.73%.

Source: Global Innovation Index

Link: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/BM.KLT.DINV.WD.GD.ZS>

Declarations

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